

A pigeonpea + rice intercropping system for rainfed uplands

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A replicated trial during 1984 and 1985 wet seasons tested the feasibility of pigeonpea + rice intercropping. Soil was laterite and sandy loam with pH 5.3, 0.04% total N, 18 kg available

P/ ha, 150 kg available K/ ha, and CEC 3.8 meq/100 g.

Pigeonpea cultivar R-60 (180 d) was grown in paired rows with 30 cm spacing. In the 90-cm spacing between 2 paired rows, 5 rows of rice cultivar Subhadra (90 d) were grown with 15 cm row-to-row spacing (see figure). The pigeonpea plant population was kept constant. Rice plant population varied because of less plot area in the intercrop. Pigeonpea received 20-18-17

kg NPK and rice received 60-18-17/ha.

Yields of pigeonpea only were 0.58-2 t/ha; of rice only, 1.74-2.58 t/ha. Intercrop pigeonpea yields were 0.52-1.7 t/ha; intercrop rice, 1.20-1.36 t/ha. The land equivalent ratio varied from 1.32 to 1.69. The intercrop yielded more than 50% of the pure rice crop yield and lost only 10-15% of the pure pigeonpea yield. This could make pigeonpea + rice feasible for rainfed uplands. □

Pigeonpea (P) + rice (R) intercropping system. Orissa, India.

Influence of zero-tillage on rice stem borer (SB) larval diapause in a rice - wheat cropping pattern

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Larvae of yellow SB *Scirpophaga incertulus* (Wlk.) and white SB *S. innotata* (Wlk.) overwinter in rice

stubble; the adults emerge in Mar-Apr. Destruction of rice stubble after harvest and delaying planting to 20 May are recommended to control rice borers.

Rice - wheat is a common cropping pattern. The feasibility of directly drilled (zero-tillage) wheat in rice stubble was studied as a possible low-cost farm technology.

Wheat was drilled by tractor in 0.5-ha plots at 6 locations in Sheikupura

and Sialkot Districts during 1985-86. The check was wheat planted using conventional cultural practices (five cultivations).

A random sample of 500 rice tillers from the following rice crops was collected the first week of Feb. In direct-drilled wheat plots, the number of SB-infested tillers (12%) was significantly higher ($P = 0.05$) than in control plots (3%). In the direct-drilled wheat plots, there were 1-2 (mean 1.2)